

Review Article

Volume 13 Issue 10

October 2024

EXPLORING FORMULATIONS CONTAINING SAHASRAVEDI; A MINERAL INGREDIENT IN TRADITIONAL KERALA AYURVEDA LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Sahasravedi is a mineral drug present in many Ayurvedic formulations used in Kerala. But its mineralogical identity is not mentioned in any of the Samhitha or Rasasastra text books. Details regarding formulations and therapeutic uses are found in regional Ayurvedic text books of Kerala. **Objective:** To review the identity of Sahasravedi, formulations containing Sahasravedi and to classify the formulations based on dosage form and clinical utility. **Method:** A detailed literature review was conducted on previous research articles and Kerala Ayurvedic text books, Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari focusing on its identity and formulations containing Sahasravedi. The collected formulation has been classified according to their clinical utility. **Result:** One of the previous research work have identified Sahasravedi as limonite. A total of 31 formulations containing Sahasravedi were identified from two esteemed texts Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari, encompassing both external and internal applications.

KEYWORDS: Sahasravedi, Limonite

INTRODUCTION:

Sahasravedi is a mineral drug present in Kerala Ayurvedic literature. Despite its mineral origin, Sahasravedi lacks acknowledgment in Rasasastra classical text and is predominantly referenced in works authored by Kerala physicians. Various formulations containing Sahasravedi are documented in text such as Chikitsa Manjari and Sahasrayoga. Nighantus provide an alternate description, associating another drug, Hingu, with the synonym Sahasravedi.

This article embarks on a journey to unveil the formulations that showcase the therapeutic potential of Sahasravedhi. A total of 31 formulations containing Sahasravedhi have been identified from the two esteemed text Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari, encompassing both external and internal applications. Among these, 19 yogas are sourced from Chikitsa manjari, while Sahasrayoga contributes 12 formulations, each offering a glimpse into the profound wisdom encapsulated within Ayurvedic literature.

METHODOLOGY:

The methodology employed in this study involved a literature review of regional Ayurvedic text books in Kerala: Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari. These text serve as primary sources for identifying formulations containing Sahasravedhi. The distribution of these formulations across Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari was catalogued to provide a comprehensive overview of Sahasravedhi's prevalence in traditional Ayurvedic literature. In addition to traditional Ayurvedic text books, articles detailing Sahasravedi were also reviewed to gather information regarding its identity and composition.

Identity of Sahasravedi:

Building upon previous research conducted on Sahasravedi; it primarily consists of limonite and its variants, hence, the distinguishing characteristics of limonite is identified in Sahasravedi. However, it's important to note that limonite is a composite of minerals such as goethite and lepidocrocite.^[1]

Mineralogy

Table 1: Mineralogical features of Sahasravedi (limonite).^[2]

Colour	Considerable variation in colour is observed, although it predominantly ranges from yellow to brown. Shades of brown on fracture surface but yellow or brownish yellow when earthy.
Streak	Yellow to brown
Lustre:	Dull, submetallic to silky
Cleavage and fracture:	Perfect, uneven, brittle
Hardness	4- 5.5

Figure 1: Sahasravedi

Formulations containing Sahasravedhi

Table 2: Formulations containing Sahasravedi in Sahasrayoga

Sl. no	Yoga	Indication	External / Internal
1	Valiyangadi kshaya	Jwara kashaya	Internal
2	Kanda sudhi gulika	Sarva roga vinasana	Internal
3	Marmagulika	Sarvamarma vikarajith	External
4	Sirastoda gulika	Siro roga	External
5	Kachooradi choornam	VP siroruja, jwara, budhibrama, hidma netraroga, pinasa, kaphaja karna roga	External (lepa over murdha)
6	Triphaladi thalam	Sannipatha and kaphaja sothahara, jwara, Swayadhu	External (lepa over murdha)
7	Balasoolarichoorna	Kshaya kasa, swasa, kukshi roga, gulma, hridroga, chardhi	Internal
8	Rasnadhi choornam	Shirasthoda, sotha hara	External
9	Pusparaga lehya	Kamala	Internal

10	Thenginpookuladhi gritha	Raktha sruti	Internal
11	Sahasravedi kannaraadi choornam	Siro roga	Internal (ksheera kashaya)
12	Chaturaaklli menthonyadi taila	Sannipatha chikitsa	External (taila)

Table 3 : Formulations containing Sahasravedi as ingredient in Chikitsa manjari

	Adhikarana / Chapter	No of yogas	Internal / External
1	Rajyakshma chikitsa	2	Internal
2	Atisara chikitsa	4	Internal
3	Athyagni chikitsa	1	Internal
4	Mutrakrichra chikitsa	1	Internal
5	Prameha chikitsa	1	External
6	Prameha pidaka	1	External
7	Somaroga chikitsa	1	Internal
8	Kamala chikitsa	1	External
9	Vatavyadhi chikitsa	1	External
10	Bala chikitsa	1	Internal
11	Nasaroga chikitsa	2	External
12	Mukharoga chikitsa	1	External
13	Siroroga chikitsa	2	External

Therapeutic Categorization of Compounds Containing Sahasravedi

The formulations containing Sahasravedi can be categorized based on their internal and external applications. These formulations can be further classified into different kalpanas.

Internal Administration of Sahasravedi

1. Gulika Kalpana

- Kantha Sudhi Gulika (Sahasrayoga): This tablet contains 32 ingredients, with sahasravedi making up 3.125% of the formulation. It is indicated for use in conditions such as ruja and arditha.^[3]
- Atisara Chikitsa(Chikitsa Manjari):

- A gulika containing charngeri, dhataki, sarjarasa, kutaja, ajamoda, mustha, ativisha, etc., includes 7.14% sahasravedi.^[4]
- Gulika with jathiphala, ativisha, sahasravedi, and khadirasaara, administered with honey or buttermilk, cures sarva atisara with 4.1% sahasravedi.^[4]

2. Choorna Kalpana

- Balasoolari Choorna (Sahasrayoga): Used for internal administration in children, especially in kshaya, kasa, swasa, udara roga, gulma, and soola conditions. It contains 11 ingredients, with sahasravedi contributing 8.3%.^[5]
- Athyagni Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Internal administration of sahasravedi, yashti, kannara, and silajith with ksheera and sitha or warm water, with 25% sahasravedi.^[6]
- Rajayakshma Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari):
 - Internal application of sahasravedi (100%) with vasa patra swarasa or kasamarda swarasa cures kshaya roga in 7 days.^[7]
 - Internal administration of sahasravedi with yashti madhu & sitha cures kshaya roga and swarasada. This yoga contain 33.3% sahasravedi.^[8]
- Soma Roga Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Choorna of ekanayaka, dhatri, sahasravedi, kannara, siljit along with sita and ksheera or warm water. Sahasravedi contribute 20% of the formulation.^[9]
- Bala Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Choorna of chandana and sahasravedi with butter cures bleeding conditions- 50% sahasravedi.^[10]
- Siroroga Chikitsa (Sahasrayoga): Choorna of sahasravedi, kannara, silajith, jeeraka, pippala, yashti, aswagandha, nagara, and gokshura with ksheera-11.1% sahasravedi.^[11]
- Atisara Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Choorna of sahasravedi and soditha hingulam with guda before and after food in the evening-This yoga contain 50% sahasravedi.^[4]

3. Lehya Kalpana

- Pushparaga Lehya (Sahasrayoga): Indicated in kamala. Sahasravedi is used as one of the four prakshepa dravyas.^[12]
- Mutrakrichra Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Lehya prepared from gokshura siddha kwatha, sitha, gritha, silajith, madhuka, pippala, sahasravedi, ela, and gokshura as prakshepa dravya cures mutrakrichra, sukla, asthi, and raktha sruti- 16.6% of prakshepa dravya is contributed by sahasravedi.^[13]

4. Sneha Kalpana

- Thenginpookuladi Gritha (Sahasrayoga): Sahasravedi is used as a kalka dravya in this gritha, indicated for raktha srava and asthi srava conditions. This formulation contains 25 ingredients.^[14]

5. Kalka

- Atisara Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Internal administration of kalka of changeri and sahasravedi for raktha atisara, with 33% sahasravedi.^[4]

6. Kwatha

- Valiyangadi Kashayam (Sahasrayoga): This kashayam includes 47 ingredients, indicated especially in sannipatha jwara, with 2% sahasravedi.^[15]
- Siroroga Chikitsa (Sahasrayoga): Internal administration of a formulation containing sahasravedi (1.1%) along with other 9 ingredients as ksheera kashaya.^[11]

External Application of Sahasravedi

1. Lepa

- Marma Gulika (Sahasrayoga): This formulation contains 43 ingredients along with 0.43% sahasravedi. It is indicated for marma vikara and is applied externally after rubbing on a grind stone.^[16]
- Sirastoda Gulika (Sahasrayoga): This tablet indicated for sira soola, contains 4 ingredients, with sahasravedi contributing 5.5%. It is used externally with taila in

vatika sirasoola, gritha in paithika sirasoola, and narikela ksheera in kaphaja sirasoola conditions.^[17]

- Siroroga Chikitsa(Chikitsa Manjari):
 - In paithika siroroga, external application of a formulation containing sahasravedi with ksheera or gritha, which includes 16.6% sahasravedi.^[18]
 - External application of a formulation containing kushta, yashtimadhu, Chandana, abhaya, and sahasravedi.^[18]

2. Thalam

- Kachooradi Choorna (Sahasrayoga): This choorna kalpana contains 31 ingredients with 3.2% Sahasravedi. It is indicated in vathika and pithika sirasoola and karna roga for moordhini thala along with nariksheera.^[19]
- Triphaladi Thalam (Sahasrayoga): This formulation used for external application consists of 34 ingredients. It is indicated for moordhini thala in sannipata and kaphaja inflammatory conditions. Sahasravedi constitutes 2.42% of the formulation.^[20]
- Rasnadi Choorna (Sahasrayoga): This formulation contains 23 ingredients, with sahasravedi making up 4.3%. It is indicated for sirasoola as an external application, used along with eranda taila, nimbu swarasa or nareeksheera.^[21]
- Prameha/Prameha Pitaka Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): External application of sahasravedi along with yashtimadhu over the head for burning sensation. Sahasravedi contributing 50% of the formulation.^[22]
- Mukha Roga Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): External application of concentrated kashaya of bala and hatha, added with choorna of sahasravedi, haridra, and krishna jeeraka over the head cures kanta roga.^[23]
- Nasaroga Chikitsa:
 - Application of a formulation containing yashti, nisa, and sahasravedi over the head.^[24]
 - In VP pratisyaya and nasasosha, external application of yashti, kushta, sahasravedi, and krishna jeeraka, with sahasravedi contributing 20% of total ingredient.^[24]

- Vata vyadhi Chikitsa: External application of butter processed from ksheera kashaya of trina panchamoola and dasamoola along with bala, aswagandha, and sahasravedi choorna, in nareeksheera.^[25]

3. Sneha Kalpana

- Kamala Chikitsa (Chikitsa Manjari): Lonamala, durva, nalikera jala, and gritha along with yashti and chandana as kalka, made into mrudu paka and filtered into a vessel containing madhuchista, vamsalochan and sahasravedi are added as patra paka. This can be used to cure siro roga and siro daha.^[26]
- Taila Yoga (Chaturakalli menthonyadi taila) mentioned in sannipata chikitsa in Sahasrayoga contains Sahasravedi as an ingredient.^[27]

DISCUSSION:

The present study explore the identity and clinical applications of Sahasravedi, a mineral drug extensively used in Kerala Ayurvedic formulations yet notably absent from classical Rasasastra texts. 31 distinct formulations containing Sahasravedi have been identified through a thorough literature analysis of regional Ayurvedic classics, specifically Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa manjari. These formulations have been categorised according to their dosage forms and therapeutic usefulness.

Key Findings and Interpretation

The research validates the use of sahasravedi, in a variety of Ayurvedic formulations. Its adaptability is highlighted by the variety of applications, from internal treatments like gulika and choorna to external uses like lepa and thalam. The physical characteristics of this mineral, such as its colour and streaks, are consistent with those of limonite, supporting the identification of this mineral in earlier work. The analysis of formulations reveals that Sahasravedi is used in variety of conditions like jwara, kasa, atisara, prameha, siro roga. While comparing the formulations present in the 2 text books, formulations from Sahasrayoga leaned towards external application where as in Chikitsa manjari a balanced approach is present with slight preference to formulations for internal administration.

Clinical implications of sahasravedi

Despite not being mentioned in classical texts, the usage of Sahasravedi in Ayurvedic practice demonstrates a regional innovation and adaptation within Kerala's Ayurvedic tradition. Sahasravedi's therapeutic potential need more investigation and clinical validation, especially in the treatment of vata and pitta dosha-related disorders. Furthermore, identification of Sahasravedi as limonite inspires further research into the pharmacological characteristics of limonite and its possible uses in medicine.

Limitations and recommendations

Although the study offers information on how Sahasravedi is used, information is collected only through literary research from 2 regional text books and previous research work done on Sahasravedi. To obtain a thorough knowledge of Sahasravedi's applicability, future research should broaden to incorporate additional regional literature and oral traditions. Furthermore, the pharmacological properties of Sahasravedi might be investigated in vivo and its mineral composition further confirmed using contemporary analytical techniques.

CONCLUSION:

The exploration of Sahasravedi in Ayurvedic formulations from treaties of Kerala reveals its significant therapeutic potential and extensive use in traditional medicine. The diverse applications in Sahasrayoga and Chikitsa Manjari highlight its efficacy in addressing numerous health concerns. The detailed review of specific formulations highlights Sahasravedi's importance in Ayurvedic medicine. Further research into its applications and therapeutic properties could enhance its utilization in modern Ayurvedic practices, offering natural remedies for a wide range of ailments.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST : NIL

SOURCE OF SUPPORT : NIL

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